

DEVELOPMENT OF MANIPULATIVES IN TEACHING ENGLISH ORAL LANGUAGE FOR GRADE ONE

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ABSTRACT

This study will be anchored on the theory/concept of constructivism that promotes people constructing their own learning through actively doing something. Constructivist learning theory is an educational theory that proposes people to construct their own learning. By doing, the student is able to develop their understanding of a concept and the instructor facilitates this. Manipulative learning materials are form of active learning, making manipulatives is a form of constructivism. In education, manipulatives can be anything! They can be specific manipulatives such as parts of speech blocks or they can be as simple different colors of paper. The opportunities to use manipulatives are endless and classrooms with small budgets can still incorporate manipulatives into the lessons regularly. This study is expected to develop quality-based manipulatives for English oral language in Grade 1. To evaluate the effectiveness of developed manipulatives in improving oral language for Grade One, the researcher-made pretest-posttest questionnaire and developed manipulatives based on the learning competencies of English 1, 3rd and 4th quarter. The researcher constructed table of specification (TOS), which serves as the guide in making pre-post-test. It will measure and determine pupil's oral language in terms of the following; (a) is the child at letters level, (b) is the child at word level, (c) is the child at the paragraph level, (d) is the child at story reading level, (e) is the child at story comprehension level, (f) is the child at local material level or (g) at risk. The researcher conducted a pre-test and post-test to the 28 Grade One pupils identified having difficulty in reading. They are divided into two groups, the control group and the experimental group. Fourteen (14) of them belong to the experimental group and undergone the test using the developed manipulative while the other fourteen (14) in the control group who will not undergo the test. Upon reviewing the results the use of manipulatives is effective in addressing oral language gaps of Grade 1 pupils on this manner the F-value of 319.9 with an associated p-value of less than 0.00001 indicates a

highly significant difference in posttest performance between the Control and Experimental groups. This leads to the decision to reject the null hypothesis (Ho) based on the p-value. This suggest that the observed difference in Adjusted Mean scores is not due to chance but rather reflects a genuine impact of the manipulatives on reading assessment outcomes.

Keywords: *manipulatives, constructivism, ADDIE, development*

INTRODUCTION

Oral language is crucial to a child's literacy development, including listening, speaking, reading and writing skills. While the culture of the child influences the patterns of language, the school environment can enable children to refine its use. As children enter school, they bring diverse levels of language acquisition to the learning process. Therefore, teachers face the challenge of meeting the individual needs of each language learner, as well as discerning which methods work most effectively in enhancing language experiences in classrooms. This study aims to develop an interesting and interactive basic level English vocabulary learning application in addition to English language learning material.

The fact that children's success in reading is greatly dependent upon their development of early literacy skills, which refers mainly to oral language development, and phonological and phonemic awareness. Phonological awareness involves orally and aurally working with rhymes, words, syllables, onsets, rimes and individual phonemes (sounds). For early learners, phonological awareness is developed through play, conversations, songs and language games. Phonemic awareness, a major component of phonological awareness, is the understanding that language is made up of individual sounds. Young children must learn to track, isolate, identify, categorize, blend, delete, add and substitute phonemes, as well as to segment words orally into phonemes and syllables. Young learners should also have early meaningful interactions with print, including and introduction to the alphabet. Children who participate in manipulative-based activities in grades preK-1 will be much more likely to excel at phonics and comprehension in subsequent school years.

Research suggests that manipulatives should be used in the context of a comprehensive literacy program that teaches the five key areas of reading—phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary and text comprehension. Manipulatives have many positive effects on education. According to Dr. Jean Shaw, manipulatives are so practical because they represent ideas in more than one way, they are multisensory, and they promote communication. These are all critical components of deep learning. Manipulatives are especially helpful for a learner who best synthesizes information through an activity (kinesthetic learner) or through seeing a concept explained (visual learner). Constructivist learning theory is an educational theory that proposes that people construct their own learning. By doing, the student is able to develop their understanding

of a concept and the instructor facilitates this. Manipulative learning materials are a form of active learning, making manipulatives a form of constructivism. The theory of experiential education (more commonly known as “hands-on” or “kinesthetic” education) revolves around the idea that learning is enhanced when students acquire knowledge through active processes that engage them. Studies have shown that manipulatives can be key in providing these types of opportunities for students. (A. Daigger & Company, n.d.) According to McNeil’s analysis of the manipulatives, hands-on educational materials (or manipulatives) tend to induce physical action, which has been shown to enhance memory and understanding in elementary-aged students. (McNeil & Jarvin, 2007) In her own studies, Moch found that the use of manipulative activities engaged both semantic and episodic memory systems, further enhancing the opportunity for students to retain the information presented to them in the classroom. (Moch, 2008)

Several other research studies have displayed similar results. A meta-analysis of 15 years of research on the advantages of hands-on learning, including 57 studies of 13,000 students in 1,000 classrooms, demonstrated that students in activity-based programs performed up to 20% higher than groups using traditional or textbook approaches. Students in these programs made gains in creativity, attitude, perception, and logic. (RAFT, 2009) Furthermore, the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP), also known as “The Nations’ Report Card,” shows that teachers who conduct hands-on learning activities on a weekly basis out-perform their peers by more than 70% of a grade level in math and 40% of a grade level in science. (U.S. Department of Education, 1996)

According to learning theory based on psychologist Jean Piaget’s research, children are active learners who master concepts by progressing through three levels of knowledge – concrete, pictorial and abstract. The use of manipulatives enables students to explore concepts at the first, or concrete, level of understanding. When students manipulate objects, they are taking the necessary first steps toward building understanding and internalizing procedures.

Not only do manipulatives make learning more fun, but they also help improve students’ reading skills. These reading manipulatives can help students of all ages engage with the text, build fluency, and develop comprehension skills.

Research Questions

The study will determine the development of manipulatives in teaching English Oral Language for Grade 1.

Specifically, it sought the answers to the following:

1. What are the learning gaps of the learners?
2. What manipulatives that will be developed / designed based on the learning competencies prescribed by DepEd?
3. What are the characteristics of the developed manipulatives in terms of:
3.1 Content;

- 3.2 Instructional Design;
 - 3.3 Technical Design;
 - 3.4 Visual Appeal;
 - 3.5 Usability?
- 4 . Is there a significant improvement on the results of the Pre-Post Reading Assessment using manipulatives?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher will be using developmental research design. This design is appropriate in developing effective manipulatives. Several instructional design practitioners have made revisions to the original ADDIE model, making it more interactive and dynamic (Kurt, 2017). Allen (2006) points out, for instance, that, in many new iterations of the ADDIE process, evaluation assumes a central function that takes place at every phase. Moreover, many of the new versions of the ADDIE model emphasize the continuity of the process and that each phase focuses on continuous quality improvements of the overall system. Dick et al. (2005) further explain that revised ADDIE models are designed to be simple and flexible. With these new processes, instructional design experts with varying levels of expertise can understand and use the ADDIE model in the development of effective instructional systems for a wide variety of learning objectives and environments. This study will be employed using ADDIE Model aiming to understand the development of manipulatives in teaching English oral language for Grade One. This design framework contains the following phases: Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation and Evaluation.

In the **Analysis Phase**, the researcher will conduct a pre-reading assessment and identify the literacy level using the FLAT (Functional Literacy Assessment Tool).

In the **Design Phase**, the researcher will map out the data obtained during the analysis phase. Design the shape and appearance of manipulatives. Existing instructional materials will be reviewed and determined timeframes for reading activities.

In the **Development Phase**, the researcher will work and create the manipulatives. Simulations will be conducted to identify errors and improvements. Performs pilot tests to enhance manipulatives before implementation. Integration of audio-visual manipulatives. Visit LRMDS portal.

In the **Implementation phase**, the researcher will utilize the developed manipulatives. Achieved the target objectives. Observe and document learners' performance. Observations will serve as valuable inputs for the evaluation phase.

Finally, in the **Evaluation phase**, the researcher will measure the effectiveness and efficiency of manipulatives. Conduct post-reading. Administer data analysis based on the gathered data.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study was confined along the following aspects:

Focus. The study focused on the development of manipulatives in teaching English oral language for Grade 1.

Respondents. The respondents will be the Grade One Pupils of Loreto Central Elementary School, Cambinliw Elementary School, Esperanza Elementary School and Panamaon Elementary School.

Place and Time. The study will be conducted during the Academic Year 2022-2024 at Loreto, Dinagat Islands.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

This portion presents and discusses the results of this study:

Learning Gaps

The following were the learning gaps of Grade One pupils as determined by the results of FLAT and served as the focus in the development of manipulatives.

Alphabetic Knowledge, pupils struggled in identifying the letters of the alphabet, matching upper and lowercase letters and naming the beginning letter of a word. Phonemic and Phonological Awareness, pupils struggled in oral reading was that they were found to be low or poor in phonemic and phonological awareness which are considered as essential skills in beginning reading.

Design of Manipulatives

The features of the manipulatives are content must enriches mastery of learning competencies, has visual appeal and usability.

Figure 2

Design of the Manipulatives

Characteristics of Manipulatives

Table 2 shows the results of the evaluations of teachers on the contents of the developed manipulatives.

Table 2

Characteristics of Manipulatives in terms of Contents as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1.Content reinforces, enriches, and / or leads to the mastery of certain learning competencies for the level and subject it was intended.	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory
2.Material has the potential to arouse interest of the target users.	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory
3.Facts are accurate.	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory
4.Information provided is up-to-date.	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory
5.Visuals are relevant to the text.	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory
6.Visuals are suitable to the age level and interests of the target user.	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory
7.Visuals are clear and adequately convey the message of the subject or topic.	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory
8.Typographic layout/design facilitates understanding of concepts presented.	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory
9.Size of the material for use in school.	3.83	0.41	Very Satisfactory
10.material is easy to use and durable.	3.83	0.41	Very Satisfactory
Average	3.97	0.05	Very Satisfactory

It can be gleaned from the Table that the teachers rated the contents of the manipulatives as very satisfactory based on the obtained average value of 3.97 with

SD=0.05. This entails that the manipulatives address the competencies the pupils needed.

Among the characteristics evaluated by the teachers, certain items stood out with the highest mean value of 4.00 and a standard deviation of 0.00, indicating a unanimous and very satisfactory assessment. One such item is the statement that "Content reinforces, enriches, and/or leads to the mastery of certain learning competencies for the level and subject it was intended." This high rating suggests that the content of the manipulatives is well-aligned with the targeted learning competencies, demonstrating a clear focus on addressing the specific oral language learning gaps of Grade 1 pupils. The teachers also highly rated the accuracy and relevance of facts (mean = 4.00, SD = 0.00), the up-to-date information provided (mean = 4.00, SD = 0.00), and the suitability of visuals to the age level and interests of the target users (mean = 4.00, SD = 0.00). These findings highlight the meticulous attention to detail in ensuring that the content is not only educational but also engaging and age-appropriate, contributing to a comprehensive learning experience for the pupils.

However, items with the lowest mean value of 3.83 and a standard deviation of 0.41 include the size of the material for use in school and the ease of use and durability of the materials. While these items still received a "Very Satisfactory" rating, the slightly lower mean value and higher standard deviation suggest that there may be varying opinions among teachers regarding these aspects.

Table 3 shows the results of the evaluations of teachers on the instructional of the developed manipulatives.

Table 3

Characteristics of Manipulatives in terms of Instructional Design as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1.Adequate support material is provided.	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory
2.Activities are summarized; extension activities are provided.	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory
3.Suggested activities support innovative pedagogy.	3.50	0.55	Very Satisfactory
Average	3.83	0.18	Very Satisfactory

The overall average rating of 3.83 with a standard deviation of 0.18 can be gleaned from the Table. This reflects a generally positive perception of the instructional design characteristics among teacher-respondents. The consensus on the adequacy of support materials and the inclusion of comprehensive activity summaries with extensions underscores the manipulatives' effectiveness in supporting Grade 1 pupils' oral language development.

The highest-rated item, with a mean value of 4.00 and a standard deviation of 0.00, is the provision of adequate support material. This indicates that teachers find the manipulatives well-equipped with supplementary resources, which are essential for facilitating effective teaching and learning experiences. Additionally, the inclusion of summarized activities with extension options is also highly praised (mean = 4.00, SD = 0.00), showcasing a comprehensive approach to lesson planning and skill reinforcement.

On the other hand, the item with the lowest mean value of 3.50 and a standard deviation of 0.55 pertains to suggested activities supporting innovative pedagogy. While still rated as "Very Satisfactory," the slightly lower mean value and higher standard deviation suggest some variability in teachers' perceptions regarding the innovativeness of the suggested activities.

Table 4 shows the results of the evaluations of teachers on the technical design of the developed manipulatives.

Table 4

Characteristics of Manipulatives in terms of Technical Design as Perceived by the Teacher-Respondents

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1. Manipulative is safe to use.	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory
2. Size and composition of manipulative is appropriate for intended audience.	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory
3. Suggested manual tasks within the activities are compatible with the motor skills for the intended users.	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory
Average	4.00	0.00	Very Satisfactory

Reflected on the Table are all items with a mean value of 4.00 and a standard deviation of 0.00, which indicate a very satisfactory technical design. Firstly, the manipulatives are perceived as safe to use, indicating that they meet stringent safety standards, which is when designing educational materials for young learners. Secondly, the size and composition of the manipulatives are deemed appropriate for the intended audience, ensuring ease of handling and engagement without overwhelming or underwhelming the pupils. Lastly, the manual tasks suggested within the activities align well with the motor skills development stage of Grade 1 pupils, reflecting a thoughtful consideration of age-appropriate activities that enhance learning experiences.

The consistent "Very Satisfactory" ratings across all technical design aspects contribute to an average rating of 4.00 with a standard deviation of 0.00, indicating a unanimous and highly positive evaluation by the teacher-respondents. This level of satisfaction underscores the meticulous development of the manipulatives and the successful execution of technical design elements in the manipulatives' development process.

Table 5

Characteristics of Manipulatives in terms of Contents as Perceived by the Pupil-Respondents

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1. It enriches mastering competencies.	1.00	0.00	Yes
2. It arouse my interest in reading.	1.00	0.00	Yes
3. It is simple and easy to understand.	1.00	0.00	Yes
4. It helps me develop critical thinking skills.	0.93	0.26	Yes
5. It helps in establishing values in learning.	0.96	0.19	Yes
Average	0.98	0.06	Yes

The Grade 1 pupils' evaluation of the developed manipulatives' contents for addressing their oral language learning gaps reveals an overwhelmingly positive response across various dimensions. Gleaned are almost all items have a mean value of 1.00 and a standard deviation of 0.00, emphasize the exceptional impact of the manipulatives on the pupils' learning experiences. The manipulatives are perceived as enriching their mastery of competencies, indicating a clear alignment with the intended

learning objectives and a meaningful contribution to their academic growth. These materials successfully arouse the pupils' interest in reading, fostering a love for learning and engagement with language-related activities. Additionally, the manipulatives are perceived to have simplicity and ease of understanding, ensuring accessibility and comprehension for young learners.

While slightly lower in mean value but still highly rated, the items related to developing critical thinking skills (mean = 0.93, SD = 0.26) and establishing values in learning (mean = 0.96, SD = 0.19) address the need for holistic education. These aspects indicate that the manipulatives not only focus on academic skills but also encourage higher-order thinking and promote positive values among Grade 1 pupils, contributing to their overall development.

The average rating of 0.98 with a standard deviation of 0.06 confirms the positive perception of the manipulatives' contents among pupil-respondents. The unanimous agreement on the enriching, engaging, and accessible nature of the materials reflects their effectiveness in addressing oral language learning gaps and fostering a positive learning environment for Grade 1 pupils.

Table 6

Characteristics of Manipulatives in terms of Visual Appeal as Perceived by the Pupil-Respondents

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1. It is engaging.	1.00	0.00	Yes
2. It is attractive.	1.00	0.00	Yes
3. It can hold the pupil's interest.	1.00	0.00	Yes
4. The images and other elements are appropriate.	1.00	0.00	Yes
5. The visual presentations are easy to understand.	1.00	0.00	Yes
Average	1.00	0.00	Yes

All items are rated with a mean value of 1.00 and a standard deviation of 0.00, which indicate unanimous agreement among the pupils regarding the outstanding visual appeal of the materials. The manipulatives are perceived as engaging, capturing the

pupils' attention and fostering active participation in learning activities. These materials are deemed attractive, showcasing visually appealing design elements that resonate with young learners. Additionally, the manipulatives successfully hold the pupils' interest, indicating a strong connection between the visual presentation and sustained engagement.

Moreover, the pupils find the images and other visual elements to be appropriate, aligning well with the content and enhancing comprehension and retention. The ease of understanding of the visual presentations further contributes to a positive learning experience, ensuring that the manipulatives effectively convey information and concepts in a clear and accessible manner.

The average rating of 1.00 with a standard deviation of 0.00 shows the unanimous and highly positive perception of the visual appeal of the manipulatives among pupil-respondents. This exceptional feedback indicates that the visual design of the materials plays a significant role in addressing oral language learning gaps among Grade 1 pupils.

Table 7

Characteristics of Manipulatives in terms of Usability as Perceived by the Pupil-Respondents

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
1. It encourages engagement in learning.	1.00	0.00	Yes
2. It contains graphics/illustrations that attract the pupils.	1.00	0.00	Yes
3. It can sustain the pupil's interest in reading.	1.00	0.00	Yes
4. It is appropriate for pupils with frustration level in reading.	1.00	0.00	Yes
5. It is useful to develop English language.	1.00	0.00	Yes
Average	1.00	0.00	Yes

Similar to visual appeal evaluations of the pupils, all items on usability of the manipulatives are rated with a mean value of 1.00 and a standard deviation of 0.00. This highlight the unanimous agreement among the pupils regarding the outstanding usability of the materials. Firstly, the manipulatives are perceived as highly engaging, encouraging

active participation and interest in learning among the pupils. The inclusion of graphics and illustrations that attract the pupils further enhances the usability of the materials, making them visually appealing and conducive to learning. Additionally, the manipulatives are noted for their ability to sustain the pupils' interest in reading, indicating a strong connection between the materials and continued engagement with language-related activities. The appropriateness of the materials for pupils with frustration levels in reading is also acknowledged, demonstrating a tailored approach to meeting the diverse learning needs of Grade 1 pupils. The manipulatives are recognized as useful tools for developing English language skills, reinforcing their practical value in supporting language acquisition and development.

The average rating of 1.00 with a standard deviation of 0.00 entails the unanimous and highly positive perception of the usability of the manipulatives among pupil-respondents. This indicates that the manipulatives effectively facilitate engagement, learning, and language development among Grade 1 pupils, aligning well with their specific learning needs and promoting a positive learning experience.

Effectiveness of Manipulatives

Table 7 shows the comparative analysis results of the posttest performance of the pupils after adjusting their scores based on pretest using the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

Table 8

Difference on the Reading Assessment Performance of the Pupils

Group	Adjusted Mean	df1	df2	F	p	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Control	0.74	1	25	319.9	<0.00001	Rejected	Significant
Experimental	4.33						

The F-value of 319.9 with an associated p-value of less than 0.00001 indicates a highly significant difference in posttest performance between the Control and Experimental groups. This leads to the decision to reject the null hypothesis (Ho) based on the p-value. This suggest that the observed difference in Adjusted Mean scores is not due to chance but rather reflects a genuine impact of the manipulatives on reading assessment outcomes.

The Adjusted Mean scores reveal a stark contrast between the two groups, with the Control group displaying an Adjusted Mean of 0.74 and the Experimental group

demonstrating a substantially higher Adjusted Mean of 4.33. This notable difference in Adjusted Mean scores hints at the effectiveness of the manipulatives utilized in the Experimental group in improving reading assessment performance.

Conclusions

1. Grade 1 pupils tend to have oral language gaps specifically with their reading skills in terms of alphabetic knowledge, phonemic and phonological awareness.
 2. When designing manipulative to address oral language gaps, the following features must be considered: content must enriches mastery of learning competencies, has visual appeal and usability.
 3. The developed manipulatives have contents which are responsive to the oral language gaps of the Grade 1 pupils and support or feedback mechanism. They are also safe and engaging to use.
 4. The use of manipulatives is effective in addressing oral language gaps of Grade 1 pupils.
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Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations are as follows;

School Heads and Administrators. They are expected to provide action plans and organized trainings for the conduct of developing manipulatives in teaching literacy.

Grade One Teachers. They are encouraged to adapt developed manipulatives materials in teaching English Oral language to cater the needs of the beginning readers in Grade One.

Parents and Guardians. They are enjoined to guide their children in utilizing the manipulatives at home.

Grade One Learners. They are expected to spend time in improving and enhancing their reading skills to the best of their ability.

Future Researchers. They are motivated to conduct more extensive study on how to develop effective learning intervention in teaching English oral language.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study has an intensive review of related published researches and studies. Obtaining relevant data from secondary sources was supported by Google Scholar online database. There was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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